

Geochemical and Nd-isotope features of Iberian sedimentary series. A key to interpret the Ediacaran-Cambrian peri-Gondwanan tectonic setting.

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The Iberian Massif presents an extensive record of Ediacaran-Cambrian sedimentary series deposited along the African margin of Gondwana. Currently, they are involved in the Variscan Orogen, where they appear in different units both in autochthonous domains and included in large allochthonous complexes. These series were originally formed in several E-W locations along the margin of Gondwana, and were later approached during dextral Variscan convergence. Consequently, the Iberian sedimentary series bring an excellent opportunity to investigate the tectonic setting and Nd isotopic sources of the Ediacaran–Cambrian transition, and also the original paleogeographic position of the Iberian terranes along the paleomargin of Gondwana. In the NW of the Iberian Massif, the Basal Allochthonous Units of the Malpica-Tui Complex have been interpreted as an external section of the margin of Gondwana. The Basal Units represent a terrane with continental affinity composed by two metasedimentary sequences, different in age and composition. The lower metasedimentary sequence consists of a thick pile of metagreywackes deposited in the Latest Neoproterozoic, while the upper sequence is formed mainly by mica schists with a Late Cambrian depositional age. Located under the allochthonous complexes, the Central Iberian Zone (CIZ) represents an autochthonous terrane interpreted as an inner section of the Gondwanan margin. CIZ presents a wide range of pre-Ordovician shales and sandstones distributed in two units. The Lower Unit is mainly composed of monotonous sequences of sandstones and shales, whose sedimentation took place over the Neoproterozoic, while the Upper Unit presents a greater lithological variety with a dominantly pelitic character, whose sedimentary facies suggest a more complex evolution of the sedimentary basins. Within the Upper Unit, the Pusa Group is mainly composed of shales deposited in Early Cambrian times.

The Ediacaran greywacke sequences from the Basal Allochthonous Units and the Central Iberian Zone, share geochemical features typical for an active margin setting as the most probable depositional environment. Discrimination diagrams for the tectonic setting using trace elements point to a sedimentation influenced by an evolved volcanic arc, probably built over an extended and thinned continental basement. By contrast, the Cambrian siliciclastic sequences show a greater recycled character and present similar compositions to those observed in common passive margins. Their highly homogeneous geochemical patterns confirm their recycled character and the greater influence of the sedimentary processes over the final chemical composition. These geochemical features suggest the development of the Ediacaran sedimentary series as related to the opening and early evolution of a peri-Gondwanan back-arc basin. The geochemical information provided for the siliciclastic rocks confirms the relatively closeness of the sedimentary basins to the source areas, which is also consistent with the immaturity observed in the Ediacaran rocks. The widening of this back-arc basin over Cambrian times, led to a greater contribution from nearby cratonic areas. This stage in the evolution of the peri-Gondwanan realm also coincides with a decrease of the magmatic activity in the volcanic arc, which favoured a more stable depositional setting with a greater control of the sedimentary processes over the final outcome. Therefore, the geochemical features of the siliciclastic rocks from both domains reveal a change in the tectonic setting over the Ediacaran–Cambrian transition, which preceded the development of a Cambro-Ordovician passive margin.

Sm-Nd isotope composition of the Ediacaran–Cambrian siliciclastic sequences in the Malpica-Tui Complex provides a single population of Nd model ages (1743–2223 Ma) and ϵNd_i values (from -13.1 to -8.1). These rather old Nd model ages and high negative ϵNd_i values observed in the NW Iberian Basal Allochthonous Units account for a dominant contribution from continental crustal sources, which suggests an original proximity to the West African Craton during the Latest Neoproterozoic and Early Paleozoic. However, the Ediacaran and Cambrian sequences in the CIZ present ϵNd_i values (-1.7 and -4.7 respectively) and T_{DM} (1288 and 1516 Ma, respectively), which support a general higher contribution from juvenile isotope sources. Moreover slightly older Cambrian Nd isotopic sources suggest greater proximity to the mainland, probably in relation to the suggested widening of the peri-Gondwanan back-arc setting. The contrasting Nd model ages for coeval sedimentary sequences in the NW Iberian Basal Units and the CIZ, likely suggests a different lateral location along the Gondwanan margin. Considering the proximity of the Basal Allochthonous Units to the West Africa Craton, the younger Nd model ages observed in the autochthonous CIZ sequences place the latter sedimentary basins in a more eastern location, probably in a section of the Gondwana margin located between the West Africa Craton and the Sahara Metacraton, with a larger input of siliciclastic material eroded from younger continental source areas.